

Comparing the quality of life and satisfaction of patients 3 years after performing partial and complete pulpotomy

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ABSTRACT:

Objective-The aim of this study was to assess and compare the oral health related quality of life and satisfaction of patients who had undergone partial and complete pulpotomy 3 years before.

Methods- 24 eligible individuals participated in the analytical cross-sectional study who were 18 years old or older and has undergone any of the partial or complete pulpotomy 3 years back during 2020 to 2021. Participants were introduced to a comprehensive questionnaire divided into three sections .Firstly it was demographic details .Following demographic there was OHRQoL assessment which included 13 items from OHIP-14 which assess oral health related quality of life using 13 questionnaire .Next in order was patient's satisfaction post treatment using DSQ -19 consisted of 11 questions covering cost, convenience, quality, and overall satisfaction. Data normality was checked using Shapiro Wilk test. Unpaired t test was used for comparison between two study groups in relation to both study parameters i.e. quality of life and patient satisfaction.

Result-After assessment of 24 patients it was found that complete pulpotomy is better than partial pulpotomy but there exists no statistically significant difference ($p>0.05$). Even though numerically minor difference was noted in experiencing pain with lower value stated in CP ($p<0.05$ – significant).

Conclusion- In conclusion, this study highlights that both partial and complete pulpotomy treatments yield similar quality of life and patient satisfaction outcomes, with minor differences in physical pain and psychological disability. Conducting additional research with a more diverse patient population would improve the validity and applicability of the findings.

INTRODUCTION:

The number and position of remaining teeth in the dental arch affects the quality of life (qol) hence preserving natural dentition is the primary goal of clinical practice to ensure patients attain the best possible functional balance¹. Patient satisfaction, which can be viewed as a result of dental care in addition to clinical outcomes, is essential for assessing the overall quality of care and, consequently, for improving dental care services². Pulpitis and its treatment continue to be a prevalent and important concern for dentists, as caries is still a major oral health concern worldwide (Kassebaum et al., 2015). So in order to maintain normal periradicular tissue in cases of dental pulp disease or injury, partial pulpotomy or complete pulpotomy is the preferred therapeutic strategy. A partial or complete pulpotomy is a type of vital pulp therapy that aims to remove the inflamed, infected pulp, leaving behind healthy vital pulp that is capable of healing³. A partial pulpotomy removes 1–3 mm of the exposed pulp, whereas complete pulpotomy removes the entire coronal pulp to the level of the orifice or cemento-enamel junction.

In the previous study executed by Lucas et al., stated that a conventional tool to analyze quality of life is Oral Health Impact Profile (OHIP), which is a standard tool for assessing oral health related quality of life¹. Slade and Spencer (1994) created a 49-item questionnaire to assess how dental problems affect patients' well-being. Later Slade proposed a simplified form of OHIP-14 in 1997. In our study, OHIP 14 was incorporated which contemplates seven dimensions based on Locker's model: functional limitation, physical pain, psychological discomfort, physical disability, psychological disability, social disability, and handicap.

In their article, Elena et al. note the absence of a standard or universal questionnaire for assessing patient satisfaction with dental procedures. To address this gap, they conducted a

study that utilized eight specific, albeit non-standard, questions to measure patient satisfaction. In our study we used a 19-item Dental satisfaction questionnaire formulated by Allyson Ross Davies (DSQ)². This engaged 6 themes which further encompassed 19 items with multidimensional aspects of satisfaction grouped into six scales (Access, Availability/Convenience, Cost, Pain, Quality, and Continuity) and a global access scale (General satisfaction).

While previous studies have concentrated on comparing the effectiveness and success rates of partial versus complete pulpotomy, they have not specifically examined how these treatments impact patients' quality of life and overall satisfaction.

Our present study was conducted amongst 24 eligible individuals who were 18-year-old or older patients who had undergone partial or complete pulpotomy 3 years post treatment. In this study, we assessed patients' quality of life and satisfaction three years after undergoing partial and complete pulpotomy by collecting detailed information from them regarding their experiences.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design and subjects- The present study was an analytical cross-sectional study among the patients who had undergone partial or complete pulpotomy 3 years back. The study was conducted in endodontics department of Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti dental college and hospital, Nagpur.

The study included only those subjects that satisfied the following criteria: patients 18 years old or older, treated with either complete or partial pulpotomy between 2020 to 2021.

Exclusion criteria were applied to subjects with the following characteristics: pregnancy, uncontrolled systemic diseases, compromised immune system, absence of prosthesis and final restoration.

A sample size calculation was performed based on a previous study⁴. Sample size of 24 participants was required.

Data collection- Twenty -four patients met the inclusion criteria and were subsequently recalled and participated in the study. The study's purpose, procedures, potential risks,

and benefits were explained to the participants. All the patients provided written consent and agreed to participate in the study.

For participants who were unable to read or write in English, the questions were read aloud and explained in their native language.

Questionnaire- Each participant was given a constructed questionnaire. Questionnaire consisted of three different parts: the first part aims to assess demographic details, second part intended to evaluate OHIP-14(OHRQoL), and final section sought to measure patient satisfaction levels through DSQ-19 was designed.

For OHRQoL assessment, the questionnaire included 13 items from OHIP-14 form⁵. The assessment featured multiple choice questions that utilized a 5-point Likert scale (never/hardly ever/occasionally/fairly often/always) across 7 distinct domains: functional limitation (1 question), physical pain (2 questions), psychological discomfort (2 questions), physical disability (2 questions), psychological disability (2 questions), social disability (2 questions) and handicap (2 questions). Respondents were asked to indicate the frequency of each problem they experienced after the treatment, using a five-point Likert scale.

In the last part of questionnaire, the participants were surveyed about their satisfaction post the treatment using the DSQ-19. The questionnaire consisted 11 questions from DSQ-19 which covered multiple-dimensional constructs of satisfaction based on the following scales: cost (1 question), convenience (2 question), quality (3 questions), pain (1 question), access (2 questions), continuity (1 question) and general satisfaction (1 question). Participants responded to the questions using a five-point Likert scale (strongly agree/agree/not sure/disagree /strongly disagree)⁶.

RESULTS:

All 24 study participants responded completely and adequately to the questionnaires consisting of 12 who underwent complete pulpotomy .treatment impact has been tested using both the oral health impact profile [OHIP14] and DSQ19 . mean age of participants of complete pulpotomy was 34.61 [21.6] years and partial pulpotomy was 31.2 [10.34] years .the study compared 14 females [58.3%] and 10 males [41.6%] who underwent partial or complete pulpotomy.

Table 1: Comparison of quality of life using OHIP-14 questionnaire between partial pulpotomy and complete pulpotomy respectively (1=Never , 5=Always)

	Partial Pulpotomy N (%)	Complete Pulpotomy N (%)	Unpaired t test	P value, Significance
Q1. Did your taste worsen post treatment	1.91 (1.08)	1.41 (0.51)	t = 1.44	p=0.163 (NS)
Q2. Did you experience pain after the treatment?	3.08 (1.24)	2.16 (1.19)	t = 1.84	p=0.049*
Q3. Do you feel uncomfortable while eating post treatment?	3.0 (0.85)	2.41 (1.08)	t = 1.465	p=0.157 (NS)
Q4. Have you become more self-conscious after the treatment?	2.0 (1.12)	1.75 (1.21)	t = 0.522	p=0.607 (NS)
Q5. Are you feeling tense after your treatment?	1.83 (1.33)	1.5 (1.16)	t = 0.650	p=0.522 (NS)
Q6. Are you unsatisfied with your diet after the treatment?	1.75 (0.96)	1.5 (0.9)	t = 0.655	p=0.519 (NS)

p>0.05 – no significant difference(NS) *p<0.05 – significant **p<0.001 – highly significant

Table 1 shows comparison in N value of the first six questions of OHIP-14 for partial and complete pulpotomy and significance of the P-value .except for physical pain dimension [P=0.049], no significant difference was detected between partial pulpotomy and complete pulpotomy using OHIP-14 form questionnaire [P > 0.05] . the higher the OHIP score the worst the quality of life.

Table 2: Comparison of quality of life (part-2) using OHIP-14 questionnaire between partial pulpotomy and complete pulpotomy respectively (1=Never , 5=Always)

	Partial Pulpotomy N (%)	Complete Pulpotomy N (%)	Unpaired t test	P value, Significance
Q7. .Do you experience any interruption while having meals post treatment?	2.41 (0.9)	2.08 (1.24)	t = 0.753	p=0.459 (NS)
Q8.Do you face any difficulty to relax after the treatment?	2.5 (1.24)	1.58 (0.66)	t = 2.250	p=0.035*
Q9. Do you feel embarrassed after the treatment?	1.83 (0.71)	1.58 (0.66)	t = 0.883	p=0.387 (NS)
Q10.Do you get irritated easily after the treatment?	2.16 (0.83)	1.66 (1.07)	t = 1.274	p=0.216 (NS)

Q11.Do you face any difficulty doing your job after the treatment?	2.166 (1.19)	1.41 (0.51)	t = 1.999	p=0.048* (NS)
Q12.Is your life unsatisfying post treatment?	1.41 (0.9)	1.16 (0.38)	t = 0.883	p=0.387 (NS)
Q13.Do you feel you are unable to function post treatment?	1.33 (0.77)	1.5 (1.24)	t = -0.394	p=0.698 (NS)

p>0.05 – no significant difference(NS) *p<0.05 – significant **p<0.001 – highly significant

Table 2 displays comparison in N values if the last seven questions of OHIP -14 for partial and complete pulpotomy and significance of the P-value .although no significance were detected between partial and complete pulpotomy , patients reported greater difficulty relaxing after undergoing partial pulpotomy compared to complete pulpotomy [P=0.035].

Table 3: Comparison of patient satisfaction using DSQ19 questionnaire between partial pulpotomy and complete pulpotomy respectively (1=Strongly agree , 5=Strongly Disagree)

	Partial Pulpotomy N (%)	Complete Pulpotomy N (%)	Unpaired t test	P value, Significance
Q1. Are the fees charged by dentists too high?	2.66 (0.88)	2.58 (0.9)	t = 0.228	p=0.822 (NS)
Q2. Are dentists very careful to check everything when examining their patients?	1.83 (0.83)	1.83 (0.57)	t = 0.0	p= 1.00 (NS)
Q3. Does your dentist usually explain what they are going to do and how much it will cost before they begin treatment?	1.58 (0.51)	1.5 (0.67)	t = 0.340	p=0.737 (NS)
Q4. Are you comfortable with the office hours of your dentist for the treatment ?	2.16 (1.19)	2.0 (1.12)	t = 0.352	p=0.729 (NS)
Q5. Do you think that the waiting time at your dentist's for the treatment is long?	3.0 (1.27)	3.33 (1.07)	t = -0.692	p=0.496 (NS)

p>0.05 – no significant difference(NS) *p<0.05 – significant **p<0.001 – highly significant

Table 3 displays comparison in N value of last six questions of DSQ19 for partial and complete pulpotomy and significance of the P-value .no significance difference existed between partial and complete pulpotomy [$P>0.05$].

Table 4: Comparison of patient satisfaction (part-2) using DSQ19 questionnaire between partial pulpotomy and complete pulpotomy respectively (1=Strongly agree , 5=Strongly Disagree)

	Partial Pulpotomy N (%)	Complete Pulpotomy N (%)	Unpaired t test	P value, Significance
Q6.Do you agree that places where you can get dental care are very conveniently located?	1.83 (0.57)	2.16 (0.93)	t = -1.049	p=0.306 (NS)
7.Do you feel that there are enough dentists around your area	1.75 (1.05)	1.66 (0.77)	t = 0.220	p=0.828 (NS)
Q8.Do you avoid going to the dentist because of the pain ?	2.16 (0.93)	2.66 (1.37)	t = -1.043	p=0.308 (NS)
Q9.Do you see the same dentist every time you visit the dental clinic?	2.33 (0.77)	2.16 (0.71)	t = 0.545	p=0.591 (NS)
Q10.Do you agree that dentist's offices are very modern and up to date?	1.91 (0.79)	1.75 (0.86)	t = 0.492	p=0.628 (NS)

Q11.Do you think the dental care you received could have been better?	2.66 (0.88)	2.66 (0.77)	T =0.00	P=1.00 (NS)
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p>0.05 – no significant difference(NS) *p<0.05 – significant **p<0.001 – highly significant

Table 4 shows the comparison in N values of last six questions of DSQ19 for partial and complete pulpotomy and significance of the P -value.no significant difference existed between partial and complete pulpotomy [P>0.05].

Table 5 : Comparison of quality of life and patient satisfaction between partial pulpotomy and complete pulpotomy respectively.

	Partial pulpotomy N (%)	Complete pulpotomy N(%)	Unpaired t test	P value, significance
Quality of life	2.14(1.06)	1.67(9.8)	t = 0.912	p = 0.265 (NS)
Patients' satisfaction	2.76(1.03)	2.54(0.89)	t = 0.871	p = 0.375 (NS)

Table 5 shows the comparison of the quality of life and satisfaction between partial and complete pulpotomy and the significance of P – value . no significant difference was found between partial and complete pulpotomy [P>0.05].

DISCUSSION:

This study was aimed to compare the quality of life and satisfaction of patients 3 years after performing partial and complete pulpotomy. While previous studies have focussed on comparing effectiveness and success rate between partial and complete pulpotomy, they have not explicitly addressed effect of treatment on patient’s quality of life and satisfaction.

The total 24 patients incorporated in the study have a minimum of one tooth conserved by performing either partial or complete pulpotomy 3 years prior to assessment. Furthermore, the question utilized in this study had three different parts : the first part aims to assess

demographic details, second part intended to evaluate quality of life and the final section sought to measure patient satisfaction levels after the dental procedure.

In the article by Elena et al, they have proposed that there exists no standard or universal questionnaire to measure the satisfaction of patients with dental procedure. To fill this gap, they conducted a study using 8 specific, though non-standard questions⁴.

The present study has contemplated a quantitative questionnaire 19-item Dental satisfaction questionnaire (DSQ). This engaged 6 themes which further contained 19 items. The study recorded a wide spectrum of views from patients thus adding to diversity to the conclusion of the study.

In our study, when comparison was made with respect to quality of life regarding partial and complete pulpotomy by enquiring through a handmade questionnaire which contributed to the convenience of patients who have filled the forms. Among the 4 tables included in the study, Table 1 has shown that only the dimension of pain has statistically significant difference ($p=0.049$), thus concluding that post operative pain for partial pulpotomy is higher compared to complete pulpotomy.

Similarly, a study conducted by Liliane et al., aimed to assess effectiveness of partial pulpotomy compared to full pulpotomy, concluded that statistically there exists 0.08 difference for post operative pain which is higher for partial pulpotomy⁷.

Also, in this present study, Table 2 has revealed that while comparing quality of life the dimension in regard to relaxation after treatment has highlighted that statistically significant difference ($p=0.035$) exists, for this reason we can deduce that patients have encountered difficult to relax after partial pulpotomy in contrast to complete pulpotomy, but there is no sufficient data in support of this factor.

Furthermore, in this study, the tables revealing the satisfaction of the patient 3 years after performing either partial or complete pulpotomy have implied that there exists no significant difference between the two modalities.

Likewise, Lie et al., compared changes in OHIP before and after endodontic treatment, and observed significant differences 1 and 6 months after the treatment. In present study, patients treated 3 years prior to study were incorporated thus allowing for a long-term assessment of quality of life⁸.

The results of the present study illustrated that quality of life and satisfaction of patients after treatment is analogous for complete and partial pulpotomy except for physical pain and psychological disability dimension, which reflected minor divergence.

This study tried to address quality of life and satisfaction of patients 3 years after performing partial and complete pulpotomy executed by clinicians at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental college and hospital, Hingna, Nagpur. The findings of the study are restricted to patients who received treatment at a teaching college and hospital, meaning that the results may not be generalised to the broader population. This limitation arises because the characteristics of patients at a teaching institution may differ from those in private practices or other healthcare settings. Factors such as the socioeconomic status, demographic diversity, or specific health conditions of the patients treated at the college and hospital may influence the outcomes observed in the study. Therefore, the conclusions drawn should be interpreted with caution, as they may not reflect the experiences of patients receiving similar treatments elsewhere.

Further research involving a more diverse patient population would be beneficial to enhance the validity and applicability of the findings.

CONCLUSION:

This study assessed the quality of life and patient satisfaction among individuals who underwent partial versus complete pulpotomy three years post treatment. The study found that patient's quality of life and satisfaction after complete and partial pulpotomy treatments were similar with the exception of slight difference in physical pain and psychological disability.

Further evaluation will examine patient demographic ,dental conditions and psychological factors that may influence satisfaction and quality of life , along with treatment complexity, duration and cost.

Ultimately, this study adds to the existing evidence that helps define best practices in dental care.

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